

THE ROLE OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEXICS FOR ESP STUDENTS

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Annotation: In this article discusses the theoretical bases of foreign language teaching and vocabulary, lexis is one of the main linguistic materials of the speech activities. So the lexis, teaching them are needed in the speech activities are the main language material then teaching lexis there have different approaches how we shall give directions there about them further.

Keywords: approaches, methods, teaching problems, pedagogical science, lexical term, speech activities. ESP (English specific for purposes.)

Teaching the foreign language is a science.

Methods of foreign language teaching is a theory of what and how to teach a foreign language at school and other educational institutions. Methods as a science investigate the processes of foreign language teaching children and adults. It plans the ways of more effective realization of education and teaching of young generation on the material of its subject of instructions. The methods concern teaching problems. It's a pedagogical science. Teaching the foreign language as a science has its subject, the methods, the ways of the scientific research, problems, aims, tasks contents, principles methods, exercises. At the same time as the other sciences "Teaching the foreign language" links has relation with the other connected sciences to develop teaching the foreign language. The subject deals with the process of the foreign language and beginning up the young generation with the help of the foreign language.

The philosophy gives us the key to the content of teaching

How Methods is based upon the progressive experience of our teachers. IT studies and develops this experience. Method in solving its problem does not reject the useful experience of the past accumulated in the field of theory and practice of foreign language teaching. On the contrary, it assimilates everything that can be helpful today for further development and improvement of foreign language instruction. Method of foreign language teaching does not stand apart. It is connected, linked has relations with other science such as pedagogic psychology linguistics and others. The objective of teaching vocabulary, lexis

the term “lexics” mean the totality of the words, word combinations. To know a foreign language means to know the language materials one of the lexical materials.

Ў.Хошимов,И.Ёқубов инглиз тили ўқитиш методикаси Тошкент 2003

English language teaching methods at schools, lyceums, colleges is written in English firstly.

Learning, studying speech activities are not possible without the consolidation, assimilation of lexics of the foreign language. Without knowing the lexics we cannot understand the content of the listening text of the read text, to speak in English or to write to express our mind in English. Therefore vocabulary, lexics is one of the main linguistic materials of the speech activities.

So the lexics, teaching them are needed in the speech activities are the main language material. The lexics must be taught, learned and studied at schools, at lyceums, at colleges and institutions. But teaching lexics there have different approaches. We shall stop directions there about them further.

Teaching lexics (vocabulary has its own aims, contents of teaching)
The aims of the teaching lexics

In teaching lexics, defining the aims of teaching is important.

Teaching lexics has 2 aims:

1 aim. The lexics must be taught, studied or means of the speech activity. It uses or a language material.

2 aim. Being able to use lexics in the speech activities is obligatory.

The main thing the pupils must be able to use them in the speech activities.

If the teacher doesn't teach using lexics in the speech activities, teaching lexics is nonsense, we don't need them.

The content of the teaching English

The aims of teaching lexics, the types the directions of schools, lyceums, colleges define the content of teaching lexics.

Now the contents of teaching lexics at schools, at lyceums, at colleges are defined.

The contents are usually written, showed in the programmes of schools, of lyceums, of colleges.

In defining the content of teaching lexics the main problem is the amount (number) of teaching lexic at these institutions. They are different there.

In teaching vocabulary the problem. How many words units the pupils retain in their memory under school, lyceum conditions, arises.

The amount of words children should acquire there depends wholly on the programme requirements. The vocabulary must be carefully selected in accordance with the principles of selecting linguistic material and taking into consideration the condition of teaching and learning the foreign language at school, at lyceums, at colleges.

Scientific principles of selecting vocabulary had been worked out. They are:

- 1) Word frequencies. The words selected are frequently used in the language.
- 2) Easily combines. For: nine room, classroom, nice weather.
- 3) Unlimited stylistically (oral, written)
- 4) Cover the topics the syllabus sets.
- 5) Valuable from the point of view of word building

According to the difficulties, the features, to the forms of school, of direction of lyceums, of colleges and to the usage in the speech activities. Now the selected lexic minimums are distributed in 3 groups according to the usage in the activities.

1 group. Active lexics which are used in reproductive, receptive speeches. It means these lexics are used in four speech activities such as listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and writing.

2 group. Passive lexics which are used in three listening comprehension and reading speech activities.

3 group. Potential lexics- are all the international words which don't demand special explanations, conveying their meaning. They are understood easily.

At the same time the selected lexics minimum may also distributed into 2 groups or these words may be grouped under 2 classes (this grouping is supposed by M. West).

- 1) Words that we talk with or form (structural) words which make up the form (structure) of the language
- 2) Words that we talk about or content words.

They both are important for practical knowledge. Words are elements of the language which are used in the act of communication. They are single units, and as such they cannot provide the act of communication by themselves. They can provide the act of communication when they are combined in a certain way.

The selected lexic minimum must be assimilated by the pupils.

Used Literatures:

1. Ў.Хошимов, И.Ёқубов.Ўрта мактабларда инглиз тилини ўқитиш - Тошкент 1993.
2. Ж.Жалолов.Чет тил ўқитиш методикаси -Тошкент 1996

3. Ў.Хошимов,И.Ёқубов инглиз тили ўқитиш методикаси -Тошкент 2003.
4. English language teaching methods at schools, lyceums, colleges is written in English firstly 2008.
 - 4.Azizhodjayeva N. N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical masterpiece.
 - 5.www.ru.wikipedia.org
 6. www.education.com